

1 Single-subduction zone for the generation of Devonian
2 ophiolites and high-P metamorphic belts of the Variscan
3 Orogen

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17 **ABSTRACT**

18 An Early Devonian and a Late Devonian high-P belt separated by Mid-Devonian
19 ophiolites is usually interpreted as two different Variscan subduction zones. A single-
20 subduction zone explains the Devonian record of NW Iberia. Early Devonian oblique
21 convergence produced intra-Gondwana subduction toward Laurussia, which favored
22 strain partitioning, created strike-slip fault(s) and a backstop in the upper plate. Slab-
23 pull induced upper plate extension, mantle incursion and hot high-P rock exhumation.

24 Extension and subduction led to Mid-Devonian suprasubduction ocean floor spreading
25 (Devonian ophiolites), which concentrated trench-ward from the backstop in the upper
26 plate. Ongoing convergence forced accretion of this ocean floor through the subduction
27 system, what was followed by Late Devonian subduction of inner sections of
28 Gondwana. Continental subduction led to underthrusting of mainland Gondwana,
29 culminating the NW Iberian allochthonous pile. Oblique convergence favored strain
30 partitioning and lateral plate sliding, and explains a different lateral position along
31 Gondwana for terranes separated by Variscan ophiolites.

32

33 **Keywords:** Subduction; High-pressure rocks; Ophiolite; Suture Zone; Variscan Orogen

34

35 INTRODUCTION

36 Subduction zones are lithosphere breaks where downgoing slabs attain high-P
37 (HP) conditions. Ocean spreading centers are sites where new oceanic crust is created.
38 Ophiolites are tectonic slices of such crust and underlying mantle, and along with
39 alkaline magmatism indicate sites of crustal extension and lithosphere (paleo)necks
40 (Gueguen et al., 1997).

41 HP metamorphic belts and ophiolites are closely related in most orogens. If
42 timing of subduction is similar to timing of ophiolite emplacement, both processes can
43 be linked in a subduction-trench complex via accretion and/or obduction (Wakabayashi
44 and Dilek, 2003). In this case, age of subduction doesn't coincide with age of ophiolite
45 protoliths, and the ophiolites would occur on top of the HP belt, or imbricated.

46 Decoupling of subducting slabs may trigger upper plate extension and ocean floor
47 spreading in back-arc and fore-arc regions (Stern, 2002). Here, timing of subduction
48 would equal ophiolite protoliths age, and ophiolites would occur on top of HP belts.

49 The Variscan Orogen in NW Iberia presents a third scenario. Devonian
50 ophiolites (400-395 Ma; Arenas et al., 2014b) occur under a HP belt formed at similar,
51 somewhat older age (420-390 Ma; Fernández-Suárez et al., 2007). Ophiolite accretion
52 occurred shortly afterward, yet in Devonian times (395-380 Ma; Dallmeyer et al., 1997).
53 Here we propose a new model to explain coeval subduction and ocean basin spreading
54 in the periphery of Gondwana during protracted convergence with Laurussia. The model
55 provides a setting for rapid exhumation of HP rocks, reduces the number of Variscan
56 subduction zones, and favors simpler paleogeography for the Gondwana-Laurussia
57 collision during Pangea amalgamation.

58

59 **GEOLOGICAL SETTING AND PREVIOUS MODELS**

60 The Variscan Orogen raised from Late Paleozoic collision between Gondwana
61 and Laurussia (Fig. 1). The existence of several suture zones has been explained by
62 accretion of peri-Gondwanan terranes during the closure of the Rheic Ocean (*e.g.*,
63 Kroner and Romer, 2013). A reworked suture zone between Gondwana and Laurussia is
64 located along the boundary of the Sudportuguese and Rhenohercynian zones
65 (Laurussian counterparts) with other sections of the orogen, which represent
66 Gondwanan terranes (Díez Fernández et al., 2016). Another suture zone is hosted in a
67 set of Allochthonous Complexes, which overlies a section lacking of sutures and
68 representing mainland Gondwana, the Autochthon (Fig. 1; Díez Fernández and Arenas,
69 2015). The latter suture zone separates Gondwanan terranes, contains ophiolites and HP
70 rocks (Arenas et al., 2016), and is the object of this study.

71 The Variscan suture zone in NW Iberia consists of two sets of continental
72 terranes separated by ophiolites (summary in Fig. 2), all of which thrust onto inner
73 sections of Gondwana (Parautochthon and Autochthon). Tectonic vergence for major

74 thrusts is top-to-mainland Gondwana (Martínez Catalán et al., 2009). The upper
75 continental terrane is divided in two sets; an uppermost terrane with mid-P and low- to
76 high-T metamorphism, and a lower one with Early-Middle Devonian HP metamorphism
77 (peak-P at 420-390 Ma; Fernández-Suárez et al., 2007). Decompression of the latter was
78 fast, under HT (extensive migmatization), and fully in place in Mid-Devonian times
79 (397 Ma; Fernández-Suárez et al., 2007). This terrane is currently disconnected from the
80 rest of the Devonian subducting slab to which it belonged, as it is thrust onto Devonian
81 ophiolites formed coeval to its burial. Ophiolites occur below and are divided in two
82 groups. Protoliths of the upper ophiolites are Early-Mid Devonian (400-390 Ma) and
83 generated in a suprasubduction zone (Sánchez Martínez et al., 2007) that involved old
84 continental/transitional crust (Arenas et al., 2014b). Protoliths of the lower ophiolites
85 were formed in a Cambrian back-arc (Arenas et al., 2007). Under the ophiolites, at the
86 base of the allochthonous pile, a basal continental terrane represents a transitional back-
87 arc section underlain by Ediacaran series affected by Cambrian-Ordovician, arc-related
88 magmatism (Díez Fernández et al., 2010). Metamorphism in the basal allochthon starts
89 with a Late Devonian HP event (380-370 Ma; Abati et al., 2010).

90 There is consensus about the processes and timing that led to the tectonic piling
91 in NW Iberia (Arenas et al., 2016). Devonian subduction polarity was Laurussia-
92 directed, the uppermost allochthon being the upper plate during the whole process.
93 Early-Mid Devonian subduction of the upper allochthon featured by HP metamorphism
94 was followed by Mid-Late Devonian accretion of Devonian ophiolites first and
95 Cambrian ophiolites later. The basal allochthon subducted in the Late Devonian through
96 the same zone the ophiolites were accreted before, thus acquiring its current basal
97 position in the suture zone.

98 Previous models have proposed a joint explanation of the regional structure,
99 metamorphism, timing of deformation, and paleogeography for the NW Iberian suture.
100 Models can be grouped in: (i) those considering this suture as that of the Rheic Ocean
101 *s.l.* (Martínez Catalán et al., 2009); and (ii) those that consider it as intra-Gondwanan
102 (Arenas et al., 2014a). The first group takes the whole upper allochthon for a terrane
103 drifted from Gondwana in the Early Paleozoic that collided and subducted under
104 Laurussia in the Early Devonian (HP metamorphism). Devonian ophiolites would have
105 been formed in intra-oceanic subduction zones that consumed the Rheic, which opened
106 along the wake of a terrane drifted in the Early Paleozoic (Sánchez Martínez et al.,
107 2007). Ophiolite accretion would result from closure of remaining basins separating
108 Gondwana and Laurussia after intraoceanic subduction. Subduction of the basal
109 allochthon would mark the arrival of the most external section of Gondwana facing the
110 Rheic after the upper allochthon drifted away.

111 Data from ophiolites question the possibility that they account for truly Rheic
112 crust (Arenas et al., 2014b). Correlations across the Iberian Massif suggest the
113 uppermost allochthon of NW Iberia is equivalent to uppermost allochthons of SW Iberia
114 (Fig. 1; Díez Fernández and Arenas, 2015). There, paleontological and geochemical
115 data don't support they were separated from Gondwana during the Paleozoic
116 (Linnemann et al., 2004), and concur with a Rheic suture along the eastern boundary of
117 the Sudportuguese zone (Fig. 1).

118 The other group of models envisages a Devonian, multi-stage Gondwana-
119 Laurussia collision (Arenas et al., 2014a; Franke et al., 2017). Devonian ophiolites
120 would represent basins that dissected the orogen (including HP belts) built in the Early
121 Devonian after a first collision. A second collision would be heralded by ophiolite
122 accretion through a new subduction zone. Burial of the basal allochthon would mark the

123 arrival of more internal sections of the Gondwana margin into the ongoing subduction
124 zone.

125

126 **PALEOGEOGRAPHY OF THE GONDWANA MARGIN IN IBERIA**

127 Figure 3a shows a pre-Variscan paleogeography after qualitative restoration of
128 Variscan thrusting in Iberia (Díez Fernández et al., 2016). Devonian ophiolites wouldn't
129 exist at this point. The rest of terranes, but the uppermost allochthon, represented a
130 Cambrian-Ordovician back-arc, which would depict a Paleozoic large-scale lithosphere
131 neck across peri-Gondwana. The lack of prominent tectonic activity in this part of
132 Gondwana after the Ordovician, and up to the Early Devonian, favors the hypothesis
133 that this neck remained as a regional feature of the margin until the onset of Variscan
134 deformation.

135 The terranes piled up in NW Iberia were distributed laterally along peri-
136 Gondwana before the Variscan collision, the upper terranes being located westward and
137 outboard across the margin relative to underlying terranes (Gómez Barreiro et al.,
138 2007). The main paleogeographic gap (offset) within the pile is observed between basal
139 and upper allochthon, interpreted to be fairly distant to one another along strike (Díez
140 Fernández et al., 2010).

141

142 **SINGLE-SUBDUCTION ZONE MODEL**

143 The two HP belts of NW Iberia are separated by ophiolites, and the age of HP
144 metamorphism is younger down structure (Fig. 2). This record has been regarded as
145 evidence for two consecutive, yet different, subduction zones, regardless of the model to
146 explain the origin of Devonian ophiolites. Polarity for both subduction zones is
147 equivalent, and coincides with that of subsequent underthrusting driving the

148 emplacement of the whole allochthonous set onto its autochthon (Martínez Catalán et
149 al., 2009). Variscan convergence in NW Iberia included a persistent dextral component,
150 from Early Devonian through to Late Carboniferous (Díez Fernández et al., 2016).

151 Progressive westward subduction/accretion within a single subduction zone
152 could explain the whole Devonian record, but problems emerge to integrate an ocean
153 basin in which the Devonian ophiolites were created. Extension is needed in a global
154 context dominated by plate convergence. Arenas et al. (2014a) addressed this question
155 by proposing the development of a pull-apart basin due to the oblique plate motion
156 setting that governed Variscan tectonics. No further constraints were given to explain
157 this basin, in whose preliminary conception required a blockage in Devonian
158 subduction, a full-plate rupture within the lower plate to create the ophiolites in a pull-
159 apart basin, and inception of a new full-plate rupture to accommodate ophiolite
160 accretion and subduction of the basal allochthon. The existence of a lithosphere break in
161 this zone since the Early Devonian questions a model requiring two extra, consecutive
162 breaks, as the existing one could readily accommodate ongoing convergence.

163 Figure 3 shows a dextral single-subduction zone model for the Devonian
164 evolution of NW Iberia. The model claims no blockage in subduction, confers a key
165 role to slab-pull forces, and exploits pre-orogenic paleogeography of Gondwana (Fig.
166 3a). Early Devonian Gondwana-Laurussia convergence was resolved in NW Iberia by
167 intra-Gondwana subduction (Fig. 3b; Díez Fernández et al., 2016). This subduction
168 probably exploited a lithosphere neck inherited from a Cambrian-Ordovician back-arc.
169 Subduction affected crust that increased in density (eclogitization) as burial progressed
170 (HP metamorphism in upper allochthon), what contributed to slab-pull (Llana-Fúnez et
171 al., 2004).

172 Early Devonian subduction was (dextral) oblique (Ábalos et al., 2003), and no
173 coeval deformation has been found over its upper plate in NW Iberia (uppermost
174 allochthon). Strain partitioning in this setting would have produced trench-parallel
175 translation of a (unstrained?) backstop in the upper plate through dextral strike-slip
176 fault(s) (Platt, 1993).

177 Increasing slab-pull forces in the downgoing plate would foster slab-retreat and
178 upper plate extension. This favors mantle incursion through the upper-lower plate
179 interphase up to shallower depths, bringing overall thermal heating to the subduction
180 system (Fig. 3c). Extension+heating favors exhumation of (colder) HP rocks back
181 through a (hotter) subduction channel (Albert et al., 2012). Maximum upper plate
182 extension would occur at the ocean floor spreading center needed to form Devonian
183 ophiolites. Their generation was coeval to ongoing subduction/exhumation through a
184 subduction channel (Fernández-Suárez et al., 2007), and took place in a suprasubduction
185 zone (Sánchez-Martínez et al., 2007), partly at the expense of continental crust (Arenas
186 et al., 2014b). In a model of partitioned strain (Fig. 3c), the region between backstop
187 and trench tends to accommodate upper plate strain. That site meets the criteria needed
188 for the Devonian ophiolites, as it would also be where mantle decompression and
189 melting to feed ocean spreading was more effective. The current disconnection between
190 rocks subducted in the Early Devonian and the rest of its downgoing slab can be
191 explained by an increasing component of diapiric exhumation (Little et al., 2011) out of
192 the subduction channel and up to the overlying crust (Fig. 3d), likely fostered by
193 extensive partial melting due to ongoing heating (Fig. 3c).

194 Vertical slab-pull could also promote eventual slab break-off (Llana-Fúnez et al.,
195 2004) and major tectonic changes (Figs. 3d and 3e). Among others, fast exhumation and
196 underplating of the remaining subducting slab would increase plate coupling, while

197 uplift would affect the upper plate, particularly its closer section to trench (Magni et al.,
198 2017). That position was occupied by the Devonian ophiolites, whose ridge(s) would
199 probably collapse upon such change. Away from trench, the Mid-Devonian
200 unconformity that is registered in the upper plate (upper allochthon of SW Iberia;
201 Robardet and Gutiérrez Marco, 2004) may account for moderate uplift due to slab
202 break-off.

203 Plate convergence remained, as typified by Mid-Late Devonian accretion of
204 Devonian (Fig. 3e) and Cambrian ophiolites (Fig. 3f) through a Laurussia-dipping
205 subduction zone (Martínez Catalán et al., 2009). Accretion of some Devonian ophiolites
206 was intra-oceanic (Gómez-Barreiro et al., 2010), thus supporting the failure of Mid-
207 Devonian ridge(s) as a likely mechanism to initiate ophiolite accretion (Fig. 3d).
208 Accretion of oceanic lithosphere was replaced by subduction of transitional crust.
209 Ongoing subduction brought more internal Gondwanan sections (basal allochthon) into
210 the subduction zone (Fig. 3g). Slab-pull likely regained importance and contributed to
211 further upper plate extension (Gómez Barreiro et al., 2007) and HP rock exhumation
212 (Díez Fernández et al., 2011). As thicker continental crust reached the subduction zone,
213 subduction was progressively replaced by flatter-lying underthrusting, in which the
214 “allochthons on top of autochthons” structure of the Variscan Orogen was culminated
215 (Fig. 3h).

216 Strain partitioning during Devonian oblique convergence explains the offset in
217 pre-orogenic paleogeographic position between upper (upper allochthon) and lower
218 plate (basal allochthon and autochthon) as the result of progressive lateral sliding of
219 terranes along fault(s) related to ongoing dextral subduction (note progressive
220 juxtaposition of white and green stars in map-view model of Fig. 3).

221

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322

323 **Figure Captions**

324 Figure 1: Zonation of the Variscan orogen after Díez Fernández and Arenas (2015).

325 Figure 2: Summary of main geological record for NW Iberian Allochthonous

326 Complexes (see compilation by Arenas et al., 2016).

327 Figure 3: Single-subduction zone model for the evolution of the intra-Gondwana suture

328 of the Variscan Orogen. Some stages are represented by plate-scale cross-sections (left)

329 and map-views (right), which also include a white star (lower plate) and a green star

330 (upper plate) to trace normal and along-strike plate movements (vanished stars show

331 former paleopositions).

EUROPEAN VARISCIDES

(EXPOSED / COVERED)

UPPERMOST ALLOCHTHON

Peri-Gondwanan continental arc (>600-480 Ma)

Variscan mid-P metamorphism

Upper plate to Early Devonian subduction

EARLY INTRA-GONDWANA SUBDUCTION

UPPER ALLOCHTHON

Peri-Gondwanan back-arc (~500 Ma)

Variscan High-P-High-T metamorph. (420-390 Ma)

Lower plate to Early Devonian subduction

EARLY OPHIOLITE ACCRETION

UPPER OPHIOLITES

Devonian suprasubduction ocean basin (400-390 Ma)

Mid-Late Devonian accretion (395-380 Ma)

LATE OPHIOLITE ACCRETION

LOWER OPHIOLITES

Cambrian-Ordovician back-arc basin (500 Ma)

Mid-Late Devonian accretion (395-380 Ma)

LATE INTRA-GONDWANA SUBDUCTION

BASAL ALLOCHTHON

Peri-Gondwan. continental arc and rift (560-470 Ma)

Variscan High-P/Low-T metamorph. (380-370 Ma)

Lower plate to Late Devonian subduction

EARLY UNDERTHRUSTING

PARAUTOCHTHON & AUTOCHTHON

Mainland Gondwana (continental platform)

No Variscan High-P metamorphism

Devonian-Carboniferous underthrust. (360-340 Ma)

NORTH (Paleozoic coordinates)

SOUTH
EAST

WEST (present-day coordinates)

